

Dihedral Angle Control of Blue Thermally- Activated Delayed Fluorescent Emitters through Donor Substitution Position for Efficient Reverse Intersystem Crossing

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Abstract

This study shows a molecular design strategy for controlling the dihedral angle of two carbazole donors linked to a 2,4-diphenyl-1,3,5-triazine acceptor by a phenyl unit. Using this approach, six thermally-activated delayed fluorescence emitters were synthesised with donors placed in various positions around a central phenyl core and the photophysical relationship between the donor position and its dihedral angle was investigated. We demonstrate that this angle can affect both the strength of the charge transfer state and the conjugation across the entire molecule, effectively changing the singlet-triplet energy gap of the system. We conclude that materials containing two substituted *-ortho* donors or one *-ortho* and an adjacent *-meta* have the smallest energy gaps and the shortest delayed fluorescence lifetimes. On the other hand, emitters with no *-ortho* substituted donors have larger energy gaps and slow-to-negligible delayed fluorescence. When applying these materials to organic light-emitting diodes, these blue-emitting devices have a range of electrical properties, the best producing efficiencies as high as 21.8% together with high resistance to roll-off that correlate with the rISC rates obtained.

Key words : TADF, dihedral angle control, phenyl linker, singlet-triplet energy gap control, blue OLED

Introduction

Thermally-activated delayed fluorescent (TADF) is producing some of the highest efficiency emitters for organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs)^{1,2}, an outcome of the extensive research in the molecular design and photophysics of these organic materials. One key design principle of a TADF molecule is to obtain minimised singlet-triplet energy splitting to promote thermal energy up-conversion of triplets into emissive singlets, therefore allowing for 100% internal quantum efficiency (IQE)³. As a consequence, TADF molecules do not need any heavy metal atoms such as iridium or platinum and still, their incorporation in devices has shown external quantum efficiency (EQE) levels similar to those of phosphorescent OLEDs⁴⁻⁷. Nevertheless, device parameters such as serious efficiency roll-off, long delayed fluorescence, short operation lifetimes and efficient light extraction are demerits of TADF-based OLEDs^{2, 8-14}. If these parameters are to be improved upon, more advanced material designs are essential¹⁵. Most TADF systems reported are comprised of linked donors (**D**) and acceptors (**A**). Therefore, the effect of HOMO (LUMO) dispersion in the **D** (**A**) moiety, the effect of the dihedral angle between **D** and **A**, HOMO-LUMO overlap in the linker and the number of **D** moieties on device parameters were logical parameters to study and guide their molecular design^{1, 16, 17}. When it comes to bridged **D-A** systems, it is known that adding the phenyl linker can induce separation of HOMO and LUMO orbitals¹⁸, however systematic correlation between the molecular isomerization i.e. dihedral effect on different positions of the bridge, photophysical properties and device parameters are not simple. Therefore, more consideration into the molecular structure of bridged TADF isomers may help overcoming the current hurdles the TADF emitters present¹⁹⁻²².

Moreover, key design strategies must be applied in order to minimise the singlet-triplet energy splitting, ΔE_{ST} . The TADF mechanism is based on a second-order spin-vibronic coupling between the charge transfer triplet state (³CT) and a local excited triplet (³LE) to mediate the up-conversion reverse intersystem crossing (rISC) of the ³LE to the charge transfer singlet (¹CT) state²⁴⁻²⁶. The environment to which the TADF system is dispersed also plays an important role in maximising the rISC rate^{27, 28}. Though nearly orthogonal donor-acceptor (**D-A**) units are believed to have the lowest energy ΔE_{ST} , recent studies have shown that perfectly orthogonal emitters inhibits TADF²⁹ meaning a certain degree

of steric freedom is required for its efficiency. So both the orthogonality of the system and its efficiency must be optimised.

The main objective of this work is to understand how the substitution position of the **D** units in different places of a phenyl bridge of a **D-A-D** molecular platform affects the photophysical properties of each emitter. As a starting point, carbazole and 2,4-diphenyl-1,3,5-triazine (**DPTrz**) were chosen as electron-donor, **D** and electron-acceptor, **A**, respectively, a system that has been widely studied due to its exceptional performance in devices^{30, 31}. This resulted in six molecules with different substitution combinations of the two donors and the molecular structure was consistently correlated with its photophysical properties. From the photophysical analysis, 2-/3- and 2-/6- substitutions of the donors have decreased energy gaps and shortened delayed fluorescence lifetimes by means of large dihedral angle of the donors. Such dihedral effect allowed for a degree of control over the energy gap and a rISC rate that, when in an optimised device structure, resulted in OLEDs with different efficiencies and roll-offs, the maximum being around 22%, and 21% at 1000 cd/m², translating high resistance to roll-off.

Results and discussion

1. Molecular structure analysis

The basic building block of the TADF emitters for the comprehensive structural study was a donor (**D**) - phenyl linker - acceptor (**A**) type structure with two carbazole **Ds** and a 2,4-diphenyl-1,3,5-triazine (**DPTrz**) **A**. A phenyl linker was inserted between the **Ds** and the **A** for high photoluminescence (PL) quantum yield²³. Therefore, six compounds from the resulting combinations were synthesized to correlate the **D** position to the photophysical behaviour and electrical luminance of each emitter.

The synthetic procedure of the TADF emitters is described in **Scheme 1**. In the case of 23CT, 24CT, 25CT and 26CT, boronic acid intermediates with two carbazole **Ds** were prepared from bromodicarbazolybenzene which was synthesized by reaction of bromodifluorobenzene with carbazole. They were coupled with a diphenyltriazine **A** to yield the 23CT, 24CT, 25CT and 26CT emitters. 34CT was synthesized by coupling chlorodiphenyltriazine with difluorophenylboronic acid followed by a Cs₂CO₃ assisted amination reaction of carbazole. Synthetic yields of the emitters was in the range of 37~74 % after purification by column chromatography and vacuum sublimation. A high purity level of

over 99.0% was secured for all compounds by high performance liquid chromatography analysis after sublimation. The chemical structure of the final compounds was identified by chemical analysis such as ^1H and ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy and mass spectrometry.

Prior to material synthesis, frontier orbital analysis of the emitters was carried out to estimate the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) and geometrical structure. **Figure 1** summarises the frontier orbital analysis results calculated from density functional theory (DFT) at B3LYP (Becke, three-parameter, Lee-Yang-Parr) level of theory and 6-31G* bases set using Gaussian G09w. Overall, the HOMO and LUMO distribution of each material is similar, but the LUMO of 23CT and 26CT is rather localized in the **DPTrz** moiety because of its large distortion from the phenyl linker.

The geometrical structure of the emitters was identified by X-ray scattering analysis. The crystal structures of the emitters is presented in **Figure 2** with each **dihedral angle** of the **DPTrz** unit at the phenyl linker identified from the crystal structure. The order of the emitters' dihedral angle from largest to smallest is $23\text{CT}\approx 26\text{CT}>24\text{CT}\approx 25\text{CT}>34\text{CT}$ which follows the results seen from the DFT calculations. The **DPTrz** moiety is distorted from the phenyl plane of the emitter by the adjacent carbazole unit in the 23CT and 26CT. In the case of 26CT, the two carbazole **Ds** induced large steric hindrance and distorted the **DPTrz** from the phenyl plane. In 23CT, the carbazole **D** at the 3- position induced distortion of the neighbouring carbazole, which consecutively induced the distortion of the **DPTrz**. The 24CT and 25CT emitters show moderate distortion of the **DPTrz** because only one carbazole affects the geometrical structure. The 34CT does not have any **D** unit next to the **DPTrz**, resulting in its more planar orientation with the phenyl linker.

The dihedral angle of the carbazole **Ds** followed the same order as that of the **DPTrz** except for 34CT which is similar to that of 24CT and 25CT. Large distortion of the **D** was observed in the 23CT and 26CT by steric hindrance between the two **Ds** and the **A**. In particular, the dihedral angle of the **D** unit adjacent to the **DPTrz** acceptor was relatively larger possibly due to **D-A** interaction. A similar effect was detected in 24CT and 25CT. In summary 23CT and 26CT showed large distortion both in the donors and acceptor, 24CT and 25CT exhibited moderate distortion both in the donors and acceptor, and 34CT

displayed moderate distortion in the donors and little distortion in the acceptor.

Although the dihedral angle of **DpTrz A** and the carbazole **D** changes by the substitution position of the donors, the HOMO and LUMO levels were little affected by the donor position because the HOMO and LUMOs are largely localised on the same donor and acceptor units. The HOMO level of the emitters was in the range of -6.11 ~ -6.16 eV and the LUMO level was between -3.47 ~ -3.55 eV as can be estimated from the oxidation and reduction potentials in the cyclic voltammetry (CV) scans in **Figure S3**.

2. Photophysics

In order to understand the effect of the dihedral angle on the optical properties of each isomer, the solution and solid-state photophysical behaviours were studied. **Figure 3** shows the normalised absorption spectra of all 6 compounds in a methycyclohexane (MCH) solution. All isomers display two distinct features which can be assigned to each individual subunit. Peaking at approximately 275 nm is the π - π^* transition of the **DpTrz A** unit and the phenyl linker while transitions at ~320 and 335 nm are attributed to the π - π^* absorption of the carbazole **D** unit. This superposition of the **D** and **A** moieties hints at an electronic decoupling, required for charge transfer (CT). 24CT and 34CT, with a **D** unit in the *-para* position, exhibit a third peak at 350 and 360 nm (onset), respectively. The spectra were further analysed in toluene and dichloromethane (DCM) with 24CT (**Figure S4a**) displaying a mixture of both n - π^* and π - π^* characters, as a result of the overlapping of this new band with the absorption of pure carbazole (inset of **Figure 3**). 34CT on the other hand, shows a clear hypsochromic shift with increasing polarity, a negative solvatochromism that corresponds to a n - π^* transition (**Figure S4b**). In both cases, we assign this n - π^* transition to the appearance of a CT absorption band, typical of some types of D-A-D systems^{3,28, 33, 34}.

Moving on to the emission, the solvatochromic effect of each isomer was studied in solvents with increasing polarity: MCH, toluene and DCM, as depicted in **Figure 4**. This gives insights on both the dipole moment and the strength of the CT state of each individual molecule. In the non-polar MCH, isomers show either vibronic-like (24CT, 25CT, 26CT and 35CT) features which we relate to a local excited singlet (1 LE) character or the mixing of both 1 LE and 1 CT (23CT and 34CT). In the more polar

toluene, all 6 molecules become CT-like, seen by the Gaussian shape of the emission and shift to lower energies in DCM - a typical strong positive solvatochromic effect⁵. Interestingly, in DCM, all isomers have nearly converged to the same energy indicating a saturating CT stabilization which is somewhat independent of molecular geometry. The largest redshift was seen within the isomers that do not possess a carbazole in the *-ortho* position, indicating a larger molecular dipole moment that correlates with their respective dihedral angles (**Figure 2**). Further inspection on the onset energy of each emitter in the same solvent shows that the most bathochromically shifted spectra, therefore the highest CT strength, resides within the *-ortho* isomers. 23CT shows the smallest shift, and the most sterically hindered of all 4 *-ortho*, restricting the rotation of its torsional angles.

For solid state analysis, each isomer was mixed (1% wt/wt) into a non-polar host environment (zeonex). The emission intensity was recorded at different time delays (TD) and integration times (IT) from early ns to late ms and with temperatures ranging from 80 to 290 K, **Figure 5** all divided into three different groups related with the rate of their fluorescence decays and the behaviour of both carbazoles in the system: **fast**, **medium** and **slow**. This allows us to 1. Determine the contribution of both the prompt (PF) and delayed (DF) fluorescence, 2. Understand how each carbazole fits into the photophysical properties of the emitters and 3. Determine the phosphorescence (PH) spectra, providing the triplet state energy which mediates TADF. Emission at long TD delays (>25 ms) was considered as PH, regardless of shape change, as to provide a consistency throughout this analysis. The onset of the ¹CT and PH emissions gives each emitter's energy levels (**Figure 6**). The DF emission dependence with laser pulse power was also measured from a power range of 0.2 to 80 μ J to confirm the presence of the predicted TADF mechanism³⁴.

As an overall picture of the decay components, all 6 emitters showed delayed emission at room temperature. The *-ortho* isomers (26CT, 23CT, 24CT and 25CT) have two clear decays (PF and DF), with the second being temperature dependent. While 26CT and 23CT decay faster than the other two, the intensity of 23CT in the PF region is also somewhat temperature dependent. 24CT and 25CT have longer lived DF but no change in the intensity of the PF with temperature which suggests that host tuning could potentially improve their photophysical properties and device performances^{25, 29}. These

results suggest that fitting of the DF component may explain the difference between these two groups. Finally, the isomers with no *-ortho* (34CT and 35CT) have small PF temperature dependence and DF components with very long lifetimes. **Table S5** shows the energy onsets of each isomer's ^1CT and ^3LE and corresponding ΔE_{ST} divided into three groups that show **fast**, **medium** and **slow** DF. In **Figure S6** both PF and DF decay rates of all *-ortho* isomers at room temperature with single or double exponential fittings are shown. In the prompt region, since there is no spectral change (**Figure S7**), all four isomers were fitted with single exponential decays.

Fast DF (with a TD between 10^{-7} and 10^{-4} s) was seen with both carbazoles close to the **A** unit and having mono-exponential decays in both PF and DF regions. 26CT (**Figure 6a**) and 23CT (**Figure 6b**) have the lowest wavefunction overlap induced by the larger distortion between **A** and **D** at the phenyl linker (**Figure 1**) and a low conjugation between **D** and **A** as a result of the small overlap between molecular orbitals. Moreover, the large **D-A** dihedral angles electronically decouples the electron rich and electron poor units, meaning that it is expected that the ^3LE states are localised at their respective **D** or **A** unit. Therefore, at a long TD of 70 ms in 26CT, a clear PH spectrum with an energy onset of 3.12 ± 0.02 eV is observed which resembles the PH spectrum of pure carbazole (**Figure S8**). The energy onset gives $^1\text{CT} = 3.05 \pm 0.02$ eV and $^3\text{LE} = 3.12 \pm 0.02$ eV for a ΔE_{ST} of -0.07 ± 0.02 eV. 23CT on the other hand did not show a clear PH spectrum even at very long TD (up to 1.75 s) and low temperatures (80 K), as the triplet emission is continuously overlapping with the CT emission, with only a slight change in band shape being observed. Nevertheless, the onset energy of the longest emission acquired was considered as PH. This fact can be an indication of a small ΔE_{ST} and efficient rISC rate. The onsets of both the PL ($^1\text{CT} = 2.98 \pm 0.02$ eV) and PH ($^3\text{LE} = 3.00 \pm 0.02$ eV) of 23CT are both smaller than in 26CT which correlates with the higher CT strength and reduced conjugation giving a ΔE_{ST} of around -0.02 ± 0.02 eV, well inside the error of the onset measurement.

Medium DF (with a longer TD, between 10^{-7} and 10^{-3} s) was seen with isomers containing one *-ortho* carbazole and the other in either the *-para* (24CT - **Figure 6c**) or *-meta2* (25CT - **Figure 6d**) positions i.e. not directly adjacent to the *-ortho* **D**. PH was measured at a TD of 25 ms. In terms of energy gaps, two slightly larger ΔE_{ST} (0.11 and 0.07 ± 0.02 eV, respectively) than the **fast DF** group were detected.

Further comparisons can be established between the four *-ortho* isomers by means of DF decays – 24CT and 25CT show a longer lived DF with a dual contribution: a fast component with a rate similar to the ones from the **Fast DF** group which we assign to the more orthogonal *-ortho* carbazole and a slow component assigned to an unrestrained rotation of the *-para* and *-meta2* carbazoles. The *-ortho D* can still induce a strong enough CT, decreasing its energy. However the second carbazole decreases the twisting of the units, resulting in an increased conjugation of the whole molecule and redshifted ³LE that does not resemble any of its units. Looking at the pre-exponential factor A (**Figure S6**), 24CT has a bigger contribution from the *-ortho* carbazole (~62% vs 38% of the *-para*) than in the 25CT (~46% *-ortho* vs. ~54% *-meta2*). We therefore conclude that, in these conditions, 24CT is a better emitter than 25CT though both could potentially become better emitters with host tuning, driving the ³LE to be in resonance with the ¹CT.

Finally, **Slow DF** (with TD higher than or equal to 10⁻³ s) was seen where both carbazole units were not *-ortho* to the triazine around the phenyl core allowing for the highest level of planarization of all isomers (**Figure 2**), particularly between the phenyl core and the **A** unit. The HOMO-LUMO distribution of both 34CT and 35CT (**Figure 1**) shows the largest wavefunction overlap at the linker which induces the highest conjugation of the six investigated molecules. This conjugation has a two-fold effect. Firstly, as previously stated, conjugation through **D** and **A** moieties serves to bathochromically shift the local excitons (¹LE and ³LE). Secondly, such increased HOMO/LUMO overlap serves to weaken/destabilize the CT state, creating an increased separation between the mediated ¹CT and ³LE states- **Figure 6e and f**. Both of these conditions result in a ΔE_{ST} which is larger (0.29 and 0.24 +/- 0.02 eV, respectively) than the *-ortho* isomers. The PH of both emitters shows similar shapes to other **D-A-D** moieties based on the same units³⁵. The decays of 34CT and 35CT were left out of this analysis because of the poor DF performance at room temperature.

Table 1 shows the rate constants of each emitter, taking into consideration each DF decay. As expected, in 26CT, 94% of the emission comes after accessing a triplet state, resulting in a high 1.0x10⁶ s⁻¹ rISC rate. 23CT and 24CT have similar rates (~5.5x10⁵ s⁻¹) though their behaviours are relatively opposite: 23CT has a low triplet yield (~80%) but the small ΔE_{ST} allowing for a fast decay, while 24CT

has a 92% triplet yield, but its dual contribution from both carbazoles effectively decreases its' emission (increased non-radiative pathways). In 25CT this contribution becomes more evident as the *-meta2* delays the DF to a point that the non-radiative pathways become more competitive, even though the ΔE_{ST} is small.

The excitation power dependence was measured on all 6 isomers in the delayed emission region to understand the origin of the DF³⁴, **Figure S9**. While a slope of almost 1 was seen in 23CT, 24CT, 26CT and 34CT indicating that the mechanism for DF is, at first TADF, 25CT and 35CT presented a small contribution from other mechanisms, particularly triplet-triplet-annihilation (TTA) which we assign to the longer lived triplet states and larger energy gaps. It should be noted that at high excitation powers, TTA dependence turns over from quadratic to linear as well³⁶ so there can still be mixed TADF and TTA that gives linear power dependence.

3. Electroluminescence and OLED performance

Based on the analysis of the photophysical data, 23CT, 24CT and 34CT were selected as being representative of the respective **Fast**, **Medium** and **Slow DF** groups and devices fabricated and tested from each group. With an optimised device structure composed of ITO (120 nm)/ PEDOT:PSS (60 nm)/ TAPC (20 nm)/ mCP (10 nm)/ DPEPO:TADF dopant (25 nm, 30 wt%)/ TSPO1 (5 nm)/ TPBi (20 nm)/ LiF (1.5 nm)/ Al (200 nm), energy diagram in **Figure S10**, the electrical and optical characterization is shown in **Figure 7**. Bis[2-(diphenylphosphino)phenyl] ether oxide (DPEPO) as host material due to its high triplet energy (3.1 eV)²⁵. **Figure S11** shows the CT and PH emissions of 23CT and 24CT in DPEPO. Interestingly, though a redshift of the CT emission is seen from the change in the polarity of the environment, the energy gaps remain unchanged, i.e. the PH redshifts as well when compared to the ones obtained in zeonex (**Figure 6**). Throughout this work, we have seen that this system is highly susceptible to changes in the molecular conjugation of the emitters. Therefore, we theorise that even changes in the rigidity of the surrounding matrix (DPEPO vs. zeonex) may induce different molecular packing, which will change the conjugation, shifting the ³LE. **Figure 7a** shows the current density (J) dependence with voltage of the TADF-based devices. The turn-on voltage of all devices was around 3.8 V and the current density similar for all three. From the external quantum efficiency (EQE) vs

luminance (L) data in **Figure 7b**, the maximum EQEs of 23CT, 24CT and 34CT devices were 21.8, 22.4, and 13.3%, all of them above the theoretical limit of 5% EQE for purely fluorescent devices hence confirming some contribution arising from the triplet state of each emitter. 23CT has the highest maximum L of the three, close to 20.000 cd/m², followed by 24CT (max. L of 6000 cd/m²) and 34CT (max. L of 4300 cd/m²). 24CT has a slightly higher maximum efficiency (though well inside the error of the measurement) than 23CT, however its resistance to roll-off is smaller: at 1,000 cd/m², 23CT, 24CT, and 34CT efficiencies dropped to 20.8, 14.5, and 5.6%, respectively. 23CT from the **Fast DF** group maintained 95% of its maximum EQE at 1,000 cd/m², **Medium DF** 24CT emitter approximately 65% and the 34CT emitter from the **Slow DF** group exhibited only 42% of its maximum EQE. We believe this trend is in line with both the variation of the ΔE_{ST} and rISC rates meaning that 23CT, with the smallest gap, has the highest recycling rate of triplets while the increase in energy gaps of the other groups leads to reduction of the EQE and electrical instability through quenching mechanisms at high current. **Figure S12** shows the current efficiency (a) and luminous efficacy (b) dependences with voltage in all three devices.

Electroluminescence (EL) spectra in **Figure 7c** shows that all TADF emitters emit in the blue region, with 34CT the most deep blue of the three and commission internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE) colour coordinates of the 23CT, 24CT, and 34CT of (0.17,0.33), (0.15,0.26) and (0.15,0.17), respectively. This appears to follow the trend seen in the solvatochromism studies (**Figure 4**). **Table 2** lists luminance, EQE, current efficiency, power efficacy and CIE colour coordinates of the devices at different stages of their operation (maximum values, 100 cd/m² and 1000 cd/m²).

Conclusions

A molecular design strategy based on the dihedral angle control of two carbazole donors linked to a diphenyltriazine acceptor by a phenyl unit was applied and its photophysical properties studied. By systematically categorising each of the six isomeric TADF emitters, we proved that the dihedral angle can affect the strength of the CT state, the singlet-triplet energy gap and the rISC rate. Therefore, donors at 2-/6- and 2-/3- positions at the bridged diphenyltriazine acceptor presented the smallest energy gaps

and the shortest delayed fluorescence lifetime. Complementarily, 3-/4- and 3-/5- substitution showed big gaps and slow-to-negligible delayed fluorescence. By applying the materials into device structures, OLEDs with high EQEs of 21.8% and suppressed efficiency roll-off by efficient and facilitated rISC were obtained. Therefore, the molecular design approach distorting the donor moiety from the acceptor can be used as a platform to synthesize future TADF emitters aiming for high efficiency and controlled roll-off.

Experimental

General information

Reagents and solvents for this study were used without further purification. Tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0), n-butyllithium solution (2.5 M in hexanes), trimethyl borate and 9H-carbazole were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. 2-Chloro-4,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-triazine was purchased from P&H Co. Tetrahydrofuran, dichloromethane, n-hexane, toluene, dimethylformamide, hydrochloric acid, potassium carbonate and cesium carbonate were purchased from Duksan Co. 2-Bromo-1,3-difluorobenzene, 1-bromo-2,3-difluorobenzene, 1-bromo-2,4-difluorobenzene, 2-bromo-1,4-difluorobenzene, (3,4-difluorophenyl)boronic acid and (3,5-difluorophenyl)boronic acid were purchased from AK Scientific Co. ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and mass spectrometry of materials were obtained according to the method in a previous paper³⁷. The synthetic path for 23CT, 24CT, 25CT and 34CT is given in **scheme 1** with a more detailed analysis in **S1**. 35CT and 26CT were prepared according to the synthetic procedure in other papers²³.

Photophysics of each isomer

For absorption and photoluminescence (PL) studies, each emitter was dispersed into solutions of 10⁻³ to 10⁻⁵ M of methylcyclohexane (MCH), toluene and dichloromethane (DCM). Solutions of 2-4-6-Triphenyl-1-3-5-triazine (TpTrz) and carbazole in MCH were also prepared. For solid state measurements, toluene solutions of each emitter (with concentrations of 1 mg/mL) and zeonex (with concentration of 100 mg/mL) were blended on a ratio of 1:1 wt/wt and dropcasted (~90 μL) at room temperature. The resulting samples were left under vacuum overnight to remove any residual solvent. Absorption and emission spectra of both solution and solid state samples were collected using a UV-3600 double beam spectrophotometer (Shimadzu), and Jobin Yvon Horiba Fluoromax 3. Time resolved spectra were obtained by exciting the solid state samples with a Nd:YAG laser (EKSPLA), 10 Hz, 355 nm/266 nm or by using a Nitrogen laser, 10 Hz, 337 nm. When necessary, the frequency of the laser was adjusted to determine emission at TD longer than 0.1 s. For the Nd:YAG laser and Nitrogen laser the earliest emission available for collection was at time delays (TD) of 1 ns and 30 ns, respectively. Sample emission was directed onto a spectrograph and gated iCCD camera (Stanford Computer Optics).

The rISC constant calculations were completed following the procedure in **S2**. In the power dependence measurements, the intensity of the laser was varied from 80 to 0.2 μJ and the emission in the delayed region was collected.

Device fabrication and characterization

The devices were fabricated on an indium tin oxide (ITO) substrate (AMG Co.). Hole injection, hole transport, and electron blocking layers were composed of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS), 4,4'-cyclohexylidenebis[*N,N*-bis(4-methylphenyl)benzenamine] (TAPC) and 1,3-bis(*N*-carbazolyl)benzene (mCP), respectively. For hole blocking and electron transport, diphenyl-4-triphenylsilylphenyl-phosphine oxide (TSPO1) and 2,2',2''-(1,3,5-benzinetriyl)-tris(1-phenyl-1-benzimidazole) (TPBi), were used. The emitting layer was a co-evaporation of 30 wt% 26CT, 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, 34CT and 35CT in bis[2-(diphenylphosphino)phenyl] ether oxide (DPEPO) layer. The overall device structure was ITO (120 nm)/ PEDOT:PSS (60 nm)/ TAPC (20 nm)/ mCP (10 nm)/ DPEPO:TADF dopant (25 nm, 30 wt%)/ TSPO1 (5 nm)/ TPBi (20 nm)/ LiF (1.5 nm)/ Al (200 nm).

Keithley 2400 electrical source unit and CS 1000 (Minolta Co.) optical measurement unit were used for current density, luminance and electroluminescence spectrum by voltage sweep measurements³⁸.

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Table 1. Time constants and decay rates of 26CT, 23CT, 24CT and 25CT, from the Fast and Medium DF groups in the prompt (PF) and delayed (DF). In the case of the 24CT and 25CT, a bi-exponential decay was used and correlated with each carbazole (¹-*ortho* and ²-*para/-meta2*, respectively). Therefore two exponentials were necessary to correctly fit the decay. More details on the calculation of these constants can be seen on S2.

Table 2. Electrical properties of devices based on 23CT, 24CT and 34CT including external quantum efficiency (EQE), luminance (L), current efficiency (η_L), luminous efficacy (η_P) and commission internationale de l'éclairage (CIE) at the maximum values, at 100 cd/m² and 1000 cd/m².

Table 1.

	τ_{PF} (ns)	τ_{DF} (μ s) ¹	τ_{DF} (μ s) ²	Φ_{DF}/Φ_{PF}	Φ_{ISC} (%)	k_{ISC} (s ⁻¹)	k_{rISC} (s ⁻¹) ¹	k_{rISC} (s ⁻¹) ²
26 CT	3.1 ± 0.1	16.4 ± 0.9	-----	15.24	94	3.02x10 ⁸	1.0x10 ⁶	-----
23 CT	8.4 ± 0.8	8.7 ± 0.3	-----	4.01	80	9.53x10 ⁷	5.8x10 ⁵	-----
24 CT	5.5 ± 0.3	21.4 ± 1.9	241.2 ± 32.8	10.79	92	1.68x10 ⁸	5.5x10 ⁵	4.9x10 ⁴
25 CT	12.6 ± 0.5	8.0 ± 1.2	98.6 ± 10.6	0.86	46	3.65x10 ⁷	2.3x10 ⁵	1.9x10 ⁴

Table 2.

Isomer	L max	EQE max	η_L max	η_P max	EQE¹	η_L^1	η_P^1	EQE²	η_L^2	η_P^2	CIE²
23CT	19288	21.8	45.9	30.9	21.8	45.8	35.5	20.8	43.8	27.5	(0.17,0.33)
24CT	5938	22.4	40.0	35.9	20.4	36.0	28.0	14.5	25.0	15.0	(0.15,0.26)
34CT	4367	13.3	21.5	19.3	9.4	13.6	9.5	5.6	7.3	3.5	(0.15,0.17)

¹. Measured values at a luminance of 100 cd/m². ². Measured values at a luminance of 1000 cd/m²

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Scheme 1. Synthesis method of 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, and 34CT. 35CT and 26CT were prepared according following the synthetic procedure in other papers²⁴.

Figure 1. HOMO and LUMO orbital distribution of 26CT, 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, 34CT and 35CT.

Figure 2. Single crystal structures of 26CT, 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, and 34CT.

Figure 3. Normalised absorption spectra of 26CT, 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, 34CT and 35CT in methylocyclohexane (MCH) solution. The inset shows the absorption of the carbazole donor and the triphenyltriazine acceptor with the phenyl core.

Figure 4. Solvatochromism study of 26CT, 23CT, 24CT, 25CT, 34CT and 35CT solvents with increased polarity: a) methylocyclohexane (MCH), b) Toluene and c) dichloromethane (DCM). All isomers were excited with a wavelength of 337 nm.

Figure 5. Time-resolved fluorescence decay curves at different temperatures in different DF regimes of the six isomers in zeonex: Fast DF - a) 26CT, b) 23CT; Medium DF – c) 24CT, d) 25CT; Slow DF – e) 34CT, f) 35CT.

Figure 6. CT emission and phosphorescence spectra in 80 K at different time delays (TD) in different DF regimes of the six isomers in zeonex: Fast DF - a) 26CT, b) 23CT; Medium DF – c) 24CT, d) 25CT; Slow DF – e) 34CT, f) 35CT. The onset of each spectrum gave the energy levels of each state. The CT emission was taken with an excitation of 337 nm.

Figure 7. Device performance of 23CT, 24CT and 34CT from the fast, medium and slow DF regimes. a) Current density-Voltage, b) External quantum efficiency-Brightness and c) Electroluminescence spectra.

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Supporting Information

Materials and synthesis, details on rate calculations, supplementary figures and discussions. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

Author Contributions

Chan Seok and Daniel De Sa Pereira contributed equally to this work. Chan Seok designed and synthesised the isomers used in this study, Hee Jun Park analysed the single crystal structure of the materials and Si Hyun Han fabricated the devices. Photophysical characterisation was carried out by Daniel De Sa Pereira together with Heather F. Higginbotham and Andrew P. Monkman. The manuscript was prepared by Daniel De Sa Pereira, Andrew P. Monkman and Jun Yeob Lee. Finally, all authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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